

Transcription of the Static Validation Study

Artifact: Focus group transcription of the static validation

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Subjects: Practitioners of the ExACTa initiative

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This document presents an overview of the six practitioners who participated in the focus group. It also contains the transcriptions and codes involved in the static validation study. We include the explanation of our approach and the discussion with the participants.

Participants

Table I shows an overview of the participant characterization. It is possible to observe that all participants had more than 2 years of experience working with ML and participated in at least 2 of such projects.

Table I

Id	Role	Project	# years	# ML projects
P1	Data Scientist	A	6	8
P2	Data Scientist	B	2	2
P3	Data Scientist	B	2	3
P4	Developer	A	2	4
P5	Developer	B	3	2
P6	Project Lead	A	2	2

We used the column 'Id' of Table I to identify the participants and their opinions. The moderator (M) of the focus group was the first author of the paper. We highlighted with color green the part of the text which contributes to generating the codes.

We translated the focus group from Portuguese to English since the participants are Brazilian software professionals. In the following, we present the transcriptions of the focus group.

Discussion with participants

Id	Comment	Code
M	<p>If you don't understand some of the elements of PerSpecML (diagram + template), please let me know how I can help you. I can go back and explain again.</p> <p><i>[Here, we introduce to the participants some concepts about requirements engineering (RE) and machine learning (ML), and we detail our solution proposal called PerSpecML]</i></p> <p>Now we want to hear from you about requirements in the context of ML-enabled systems. Based on your experience and the problems/challenges you face in practice regarding requirements in the context of ML, does PerSpecML address a relevant industry problem?</p>	
P6	<p>I've been working for just over 2 years with ML systems. I'm not an expert, but to the best of my knowledge, there is a lack of tools and methods that help in understanding and detailing these types of requirements. My feeling is that solution proposals of this type do not reach the industry. This leads to mismatches between practitioners and literature.</p>	01) Lack of methods for supporting RE for ML
P3	<p>I agree with P6, in my opinion, there is a lack of methods following this line. I've never seen a standard or guideline shedding light on how to specify and document ML-enabled systems.</p>	01) Lack of methods for supporting RE for ML
P2	<p>From my side, I see lean inceptions as the closest thing to focused requirements for ML. I know this approach is not focused on ML-based systems, but in my opinion it has worked well. I also know that it has limitations, but this could be improved.</p>	02) Other techniques for supporting RE for ML
P4	<p>I'm curious to see a formal specification of an ML component. Based on my experience, these definitions are informal and emerge as the project progresses.</p>	01) Lack of methods for supporting RE for ML
M	Does anyone have any comments?	
P4	<p>ML is a process of continuous experimentation. This is well known. Requirements could not be different in this context. I see that the process of designing an ML-enabled system is based on empirical knowledge, which makes it highly dependent on trial-and-error experimentation. At the beginning of the projects, initial requirements are defined, but at the end of the project these requirements are very different. As projects progress, these requirements change. I think this uncertainty could be reduced to avoid reworks.</p>	03) Need for experimentation

P6	I feel that the ML development team often transmits skepticism to customers, not because of the lack of knowledge of its members, but because of the lack of an established process to define what can be done in ML terms with what the client makes available.	01) Lack of methods for supporting RE for ML
M	I did not understand your point. What do you want to say with “what can be done in ML terms with what customers make available”. Could you give some examples?	
P6	Sure, I mean, customers give us many files with data and verbal information about the business. But, what can we do with this to better align these recursos with what customers want to do?	N/A
M	Ok. Let's talk about the requirements specifications of Project A and B that were presented several minutes ago. We introduced two artifacts: the first was the ML Perspective-based diagram of tasks and concerns, and the second was the specification template. Feel free to bring up any element that you found important or relevant, but also any component that you consider could be improved or that was not clear.	
P4	I found the artifacts super interesting. In my view, the way we work is well mapped in the diagram. I can clearly see definitions of the ML project, model and data requirements, and user experiences aspects that typically I dont concern.	04) Positive opinion about PerSpecML
P6	I also found it interesting. I think this maps well the process that we follow in the company. Really the content is quite extensive, a lot of information, but also mapped the ML process, the flow is very interesting. By looking at the task-concern relationships, I was able to identify dependencies and influences as intended. I think that's clear.	04) Positive opinion about PerSpecML 05) Meaningful relationships
P2	I consider these perspectives and the overview provided by the diagram very useful. I'm thinking: normally at the beginning of our ML projects, the team focuses on well-known requirements such as understanding the problem to be solved, obtaining data, and some performance metrics that the model must achieve. Just that. As the team faces ML tasks, concerns arise that are not considered at the beginning of the projects. This can negatively impact project management. So I think this overview of ML that provides the approach is cool.	04) Positive opinion about PerSpecML
P5	Let me understand something. The idea is the following: if someone is working with a ML project, someone has to read the perspective diagram and then fill the specification template, right?	
M	Yes, the purpose of the diagram is to allow the requirements engineer or other professional responsible for these functions to analyze the different tasks and concerns from each perspective	

	so that they can be analyzed with the different stakeholders. With this analysis done, the ML specification template can be filled with the components that apply.	
P5	I didn't understand the ML tasks that have 2 colors. What is the purpose of that?	
M	Note that there are specific concerns that can benefit from involving more than one stakeholder in the analysis. For example, the execution engine concern is a yellow-blue gradient since it involves knowledge in charge of the data scientist and may also involve expertise of the software engineer that provides the ML-enabled system infrastructure.	
P5	I consider this resource of the proposal very important. In many times, collaborative work is essential to be successful and achieve the value of what is planned. In ML projects this should be mandatory since multidisciplinary teams need to communicate well.	04) Positive opinion about PerSpecML
P1	From what I've seen, looking at the ML diagram allowed me to have an overview of the requirements that can be analyzed from the early stages of the project and the requirements that are defined as the project progresses. But I have one doubt. Did you ever consider a roadmap to follow the diagram? For example: it would be nice to have a step-by-step, activity enumeration, template filling flow of the approach.	06) Overview of the process - suitability of the solution 07) Improvements for PerSpecML - instructions to read the diagram
P2	I agree with P1. It is not clear to me what is the order of execution of the diagram. A roadmap would be very important to give an idea to those involved in the project about the activities that later on will have to be attended by X or Y professionals. So I see this diagram as a planner that can help ML teams identify upcoming tasks. But for that, you need to have a roadmap that allows you to map what is done first, what dependencies there are, what are the possible paths.	07) Improvements for PerSpecML - instructions to read the diagram
P5	I also have suggestions. In my opinion the diagram needs to simplify some tasks. In the model perspective, the number of tasks seems large in practice, perhaps it would be interesting to reduce the format.	07) Improvements for our approach - simplifying tasks
P3	Another point I would like to highlight is the following. I've worked on several projects developing the dashboards combining predictions and preferences of customers and end-users. Typically, I see user experience requirements take a back seat. Okay, we make an effort to identify some requirements at the beginning of the projects, but that's not enough in my opinion. The relevance of user experience in the success of this type of system forces us to reconsider this.	08) Awareness on important concerns 09) Importance of the user experience perspective

<p>P5</p>	<p>I agree with P3 but in the case of the ML objective perspective. I also understand the need to consider data, model, user and infrastructure, but in my opinion, the functional behavior of ML models, which is reflected in the goals and objectives, is crucial. I think that perspective is really the starting point of everything. This is where the team must really understand what the customer wants to determine how ML can help them to achieve their goals.</p>	<p>08) Awareness on important concerns</p> <p>10) Importance of the ML objective perspective</p>
<p>P3</p>	<p>I have a suggestion regarding the distribution of some tasks and concerns of the diagram. Look at the ML objective perspective. The 'define ML objectives' task has independent concerns that could be part of separate tasks. In my opinion the leading indicators are not goals but are important metrics to achieve the objectives.</p>	<p>07) Improvements for our approach - breaking down some tasks</p>
<p>M</p>	<p>This feedback is very important for us. Now, regarding improvements, elements of the artifacts that are not clear, feel free to mention and express your ideas.</p>	
<p>P4</p>	<p>Well, an ML project involves many activities, both technical and non-technical. I think this could be reflected in the artifacts and made clearer, as differentiating the types of tasks, concerns in this case, helps to better address the responsibilities of those involved.</p>	<p>07) Improvements for our approach</p>
<p>P2</p>	<p>When you introduced the specification of the projects, to be honest, I didn't like the template so much. In my opinion, the specification template is very simple, I mean, it does not have relationships or related tasks like the diagram.</p> <p>Regarding the completeness of tasks and concerns, I feel that maybe something is missing. I don't know exactly what's missing, I just keep thinking that ML is a discipline that involves many areas such as mathematics, statistics, engineering... so it would be good for you to review and evaluate if something is missing.</p>	<p>07) Improvements of our approach - specification template.</p> <p>07) Improvements for our approach - completeness.</p>
<p>M</p>	<p>I agree with your point of view. In fact, the scope of our work did not consider dividing or differentiating this issue from technical tasks. An improvement of the approach could consider this. Thanks.</p> <p>Now we are going to fill out a questionnaire where you can mention the main benefits and limitations of using our approach. With this we also want to validate what was said here. Any questions please let me know.</p>	

In total, we identified the following list of codes attached to the transcription.

- 01 - lack of methods for supporting requirements for ML
- 02 - other techniques for supporting requirements for ML
- 03 - need for experimentation
- 04 - Positive position about our approach
- 05 - Meaningful relationships
- 06 - Overview of the process
- 07 - Improvements for our approach
- 08 - awareness on important concerns
- 09 - Important of the user experience perspective
- 10 - importance of the ML objective perspective